

Q10) How do you perceive the importance of using AI-based programming assistants in the following situations?

Professional Experience

2 years or less of professional experience (n=10)

3 to 9 years of professional experience (n=9)

10 years or more of professional experience (n=10)

Type of Work

Mainly-legacy system (n=8)

Mainly new applications (n=6)

Balance (n=15)

Q13) How do you estimate how often you use the tools below in a workweek?

Mainly-legacy system (n=8)

Mainly new applications (n=6)

Balance (n=15)

